

Synthesis, spectral characterization, electrochemical behaviour and antibacterial activity of mixed ligand copper(II) and zinc(II) complexes of 3,4-substituted β -diketones with 2,2'-bipyridine

N. Raman

Department of Chemistry, VHNSN College, Virudhunagar-626 001, Tamilnadu, India

E-mail : drn_raman@yahoo.co.in

Manuscript received 5 May 2008, revised 13 August 2008, accepted 2 September 2008

Abstract : Six new mixed-ligand copper(II) and zinc(II) complexes of the composition $[\text{ML}(\text{bpy})_2]\text{Cl}_2$, where $\text{M} = \text{Cu}^{\text{II}}/\text{Zn}^{\text{II}}$; $\text{L} = 3,4$ -substituted β -diketone derived from salicylaldehyde and acetylacetone/methylacetoacetate/acetoacetanilide and $\text{bpy} = 2,2'$ -bipyridine, were synthesized. They were characterized by usual analytical and spectral techniques. The data show that the complexes exhibit octahedral geometry. The powder XRD study confirms the structural similarity of the copper and zinc complexes. The salient features of their electrochemical behaviour have been discussed. The antibacterial activities of the free ligands and their complexes have been screened against various microorganisms (both Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria). The data indicate that the complexes are highly active than the free ligands.

Keywords : Mixed-ligand complexes, bipyridine complexes, β -diketone complexes, electrochemical behaviour, antibacterial activity.

Introduction

Over the last few years, the chemistry of β -diketone containing compounds has become an active area of research¹⁻⁴. The coordination compounds of transition metal(II) ions with ligands containing nitrogen and oxygen as donor atoms have been the subject of considerable investigations and the greatest interest has been in the complexes with ammonia or ethylenediamine and analogous as nitrogen ligands. Different and interesting behaviour was observed by substituting these ligands with other nitrogen containing chelate groups such as *o*-phenanthroline or 2,2'-bipyridine⁵⁻⁷ with transition metal(II) ions. There has been considerable interest in the study of mixed-ligand coordinated complexes of transition metals in view of their unusual magnetic properties, catalytic activities and biochemical behaviour⁵⁻⁸. Moreover, the structural characterization of the mixed-ligand complexes may be interesting due to various ratios of coordinations like 1 : 1, 1 : 2, 1 : 3 etc. The literature search reveals that no work has been reported on mixed-ligand complexes of 3,4-substituted neutral β -diketones with 2,2'-bipyridine⁹⁻¹³. In view of the limited information available regarding the spectroscopic properties and the structural features of mixed-ligand copper(II) and zinc(II) chelates containing bipyridine ligand, the present

study is undertaken in order to investigate the affinity of nitrogenous bases toward copper(II) and zinc(II) in the presence of neutral β -diones. In continuation of my study on biologically important carbonyl compounds^{14,15}, I herein report the synthesis and characterization of mixed-ligand complexes of copper(II) and zinc(II) ions with 2,2'-bipyridine and 3,4-substituted β -diketones.

Results and discussion

All the complexes are air stable. The analytical data of the synthesized compounds and their physical properties are summarized in Table 1. The analytical data correspond well with the general formula $[\text{ML}(\text{bpy})_2]\text{Cl}_2$, where $\text{bpy} = 2,2'$ -bipyridine and $\text{L} = \text{L}^1/\text{L}^2/\text{L}^3$. Higher conductance values of metal complexes which support their 1 : 2 electrolytic nature and are consistent with other related metal complexes¹⁶.

FAB-mass spectra : The copper complex $[\text{CuL}^1(\text{bpy})_2]\text{Cl}_2$ shows molecular ion peak at 651 *m/z*. The peak at 189 *m/z* is due to the high intensity base peak corresponding to the fragment, $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_9\text{O}_3$ and the other fragmentation peaks observed at 232, 171, 443, 411, 155 and 107 are due to $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_4$, $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_8\text{O}_2$, $[\text{Cu}(\text{bpy})_2]\text{Cl}_2$, $[\text{Cu}(\text{bpy})_2]\text{Cl}$, bpy and $\text{C}_7\text{H}_6\text{O}$ respectively. The data indicate that the stoichiometry of the metal chelates is $[\text{ML}^1(\text{bpy})_2]\text{Cl}_2$.

Table 1. Physical and analytical data of the synthesized complexes

Compd./ Complex	Colour	Melt/ dec. pt. (°C)	Analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)					Formula weight (Calcd.)	λ_M ($\Omega^{-1} \text{ m}^2$) $\text{mol}^{-1} \times 10^{-3}$	μ_{eff} (B.M.)
			M	C	H	N	Cl			
$\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_3$ (L ¹)	Yellow	95	-	70.5 (70.6)	5.9 (5.9)	-	-	204.2	2.1	-
$\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_4$ (L ²)	Yellow	106	-	65.4 (65.4)	5.5 (5.5)	-	-	220.2	3.3	-
$\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{15}\text{NO}_3$ (L ³)	Yellow	115	-	72.0 (72.6)	4.78 (5.37)	4.6 (4.9)	-	28.13	1.8	-
$[\text{CuL}^1(\text{bpy})_2]\text{Cl}_2$	Green	219	9.7 (9.8)	59.1 (59.0)	4.2 (4.3)	7.9 (8.6)	10.8 (10.9)	651.0	105.5	1.73
$[\text{CuL}^2(\text{bpy})_2]\text{Cl}_2$	Green	225	9.5 (9.5)	57.5 (57.6)	4.2 (4.3)	8.1 (8.4)	10.6 (10.6)	667.0	95.6	1.75
$[\text{CuL}^3(\text{bpy})_2]\text{Cl}_2$	Green	240	8.7 (8.7)	60.9 (61.0)	4.2 (4.3)	9.6 (9.6)	9.7 (9.7)	728.1	120.2	1.74
$[\text{ZnL}^1(\text{bpy})_2]\text{Cl}_2$	Colourless	243	10.0 (10.0)	58.9 (58.9)	4.3 (4.3)	8.3 (8.6)	10.9 (10.9)	652.8	112.8	-
$[\text{ZnL}^2(\text{bpy})_2]\text{Cl}_2$	Colourless	245	9.8 (9.8)	57.0 (57.5)	4.1 (4.2)	8.1 (8.4)	10.6 (10.6)	668.0	98.9	-
$[\text{ZnL}^3(\text{bpy})_2]\text{Cl}_2$	Colourless	238	8.9 (8.9)	60.9 (60.9)	4.1 (4.3)	9.4 (9.7)	9.7 (9.7)	729.9	89.6	-

¹H and ¹³C NMR spectra : The ¹H NMR and ¹³C NMR spectra of the $[\text{ZnL}^2(\text{bpy})_2]\text{Cl}_2$ were recorded in DMSO-*d*₆ at room temperature. The ¹H NMR and ¹³C NMR spectral values of the above complex are given in Tables 2 and 3 respectively.

IR spectra : The IR spectra of all the complexes and ligands under study show broad bands in the region 3000–3250 cm^{-1} indicates that the phenolic -OH group present in the salicylaldehyde moiety in all the ligands is not involved in coordination. All the ligands show a prominent peak at *ca.* 1720 cm^{-1} corresponding to $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{O}}$ keto group. A slight downfield shift has been observed in all the spectra of the complexes. The terminal chelating mode

of bpy is typically characterized by two intense, sharp peaks of nearly equal intensities at *ca.* 1580 cm^{-1} (ring stretching mode of bpy). An asymmetric doublet or a single strong broad feature in the same range, however, indicates the presence of bischelating mode¹⁷. In the free bpy molecule, strong interactions between C=C and C=N give rise to two groups of doublets (1650, 1552 cm^{-1} and 1480, 1445 cm^{-1}).

These bands undergo remarkable changes due to coordination and new bands are found to appear in the spectra of complexes around 1590 and 1565 cm^{-1} confirming the coordination nature of the bpy ligand through both the nitrogen atoms. The conclusive evidence of bonding of

Table 2. The ¹H NMR spectral data and their assignments

Compd.	C ₆ H ₅ multiplet	-C-CH ₃	-OCH ₃	-OH	Ph-NH
L ¹	7.2–7.6	2.8	-	11.42	-
Zn[L ¹ (bpy) ₂] ₂ Cl ₂	7.1–7.6	2.6	-	11.41	-
L ²	7.4–7.6	3.7	2.55	11.75	-
Zn[L ² (bpy) ₂] ₂ Cl ₂	7.3–7.4	3.5	3.0	11.74	-
L ³	6.9–7.4	3.9	-	11.82	7.8
Zn[L ³ (bpy) ₂] ₂ Cl ₂	7.1–7.5	3.6	-	11.80	7.7

Table 3. ^{13}C NMR spectral data of the $[\text{ZnL}^2(\text{bpy})_2]\text{Cl}_2$ complex

Values (ppm)	Assignments	Values (ppm)	Assignments
26.5	C ₁	149.6	C ₁₀
195.2	C ₂	198.3	C ₁₁
118.1	C ₃	30.1	C ₁₂
148.5	C ₄	147.1	C _{1'}
154.6	C ₅	116.1	C _{2'}
158.4	C ₆	130.8	C _{3'}
122.2	C ₇	134.6	C _{4'}
126.5	C ₈	125.0	C _{5'}
140.5	C ₉		

ligand to metal ion is indicated by the appearance of bands due to $\nu_{\text{M-O}}$ at $485\text{--}510\text{ cm}^{-1}$ region and $\nu_{\text{M-N}}$ at $410\text{--}420\text{ cm}^{-1}$ region. These values are comparable with other reported complexes¹⁸.

Fig. 1. ESR spectrum of $[\text{CuL}^1(\text{bpy})_2]\text{Cl}_2$ at (a) 77 K and (b) 300 K in DMSO solution.

Electronic absorption spectra : The electronic absorption spectra of $\text{L}^1/\text{L}^2/\text{L}^3$ and their copper complexes were recorded at 300 K using suitable solvent. The magnetic moment for the Cu^{II} chelates correspond to one unpaired electron. The electronic absorption spectra of Cu^{II} chelates show bands at ca. $12626\text{--}12919\text{ cm}^{-1}$, which presumably contain *d-d* transition¹⁹. The band may be due to ${}^2E_g \rightarrow {}^2T_{2g}$ transition for distorted octahedral geometry. The other complexes show similar type of structural features.

ESR spectra : The ESR spectra of Cu^{II} complexes, recorded in DMSO solution at 300 K and 77 K, are given in Fig. 1. The ESR parameters are given in Table 4. All the three Cu^{II} complexes at 300 K give one intense absorption band in the high field region and are isotropic due to tumbling motion of the molecules. However, these complexes in frozen state show four well-resolved peaks with low intensities in the low field region and one intense peak in the high field region. The magnetic moment values of these complexes range from 1.72 to 1.75 B.M., corresponding to one unpaired electron, indicating that the complex is mononuclear. This fact is also evident from the absence of a half field signal, observed in the spectrum at 1600 G due to the $m_s = \pm 2$ transitions, ruling out any Cu-Cu interaction²⁰. The spin Hamiltonian parameters of the complexes are given in Table 4.

Table 4. The spin Hamiltonian parameters of Cu^{II} complexes in DMSO at 300 and 77 K

Complex	$A_{\parallel} \times 10^{-4}$ (cm^{-1})	$A_{\perp} \times 10^{-4}$ (cm^{-1})	$A_{\text{iso}} \times 10^{-4}$ (cm^{-1})	g_{\parallel}	g_{\perp}	g_{iso}	α^2	β^2	γ^2
$[\text{CuL}^1(\text{bpy})_2]\text{Cl}_2$	170.4	45.00	76.66	2.3150	2.06	2.056	0.8507	0.7169	0.5098
$[\text{CuL}^2(\text{bby})_2]\text{Cl}_2$	169.8	54.54	76.66	2.3559	2.062	2.057	0.8909	0.7566	0.5634
$[\text{CuL}^3(\text{bpy})_2]\text{Cl}_2$	173.04	27.24	80.00	2.3263	2.06	2.066	0.8694	0.7157	0.5291

From the observed values, it is clear that $g_{\parallel} > g_{\perp} > 2.00$ and $A_{\parallel} > A_{\perp}$ which suggests that the complex exhibits in octahedral geometry and the unpaired electron lies predominantly in the $d_{x^2-y^2}$ orbital²¹⁻²³.

It is well known²¹ that g_{\parallel} is 2.4 for copper-oxygen bonds and 2.3 for copper-nitrogen bonds. For the present copper complexes, $g_{\parallel} = 2.3559$ in $[\text{CuL}^1(\text{bpy})_2]\text{Cl}_2$, 2.3389 in $[\text{CuL}^2(\text{bpy})_2]\text{Cl}_2$ and 2.3487 in $[\text{CuL}^3(\text{bpy})_2]\text{Cl}_2$, which are in between 2.3-2.4. This conforms the presence of mixed copper-nitrogen and copper-oxygen bonds in these chelates. Molecular orbital coefficients, α^2 (covalent in-plane σ -bonding) and β^2 (covalent in-plane π -bonding), were calculated using the following equations :

$$\alpha^2 = -(A_{\parallel}/0.036) + (g_{\parallel} - 2.0023) + 3/7(g_{\perp} - 2.0023) + 0.04$$

$$\beta^2 = (g_{\parallel} - 2.0023)E / -8\lambda\alpha^2$$

where $\lambda = 828 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ for free ion and E is the electronic transition energy of ${}^2E_{2g} \rightarrow {}^2T_{2g}$. From Table 4, it is evident that the σ -bonding is more covalent than the in-plane π -bonding.

Based on the above analytical and spectral data, the proposed structures of the ligand and the complex are given in Fig. 2 and Fig. 3.

Electrochemical behaviour : The cyclic voltammogram of the $[\text{CuL}^1(\text{bpy})_2]\text{Cl}_2$ complex in DMSO at 300 K in the potential range +0.1 to -1.4 V are shown in Fig. 4

R = -CH₃; 3-salicylideneacetylacetone (L¹)
 R = -OCH₃; 3-salicylideneacetylacetate (L²)
 R = -NHC₆H₅; 3-salicylideneacetylacetanilide (L³)

Fig. 2. Structure of the ligand.

Fig. 3. Structure of the complexes.

Fig. 4. Cyclic voltammogram of $[\text{CuL}^1(\text{bpy})_2]\text{Cl}_2$ complex in DMSO solution (0.1 M TBAP); scan rate 100 mV s⁻¹.

and the data of the complexes are listed in Table 5 which show a well-defined redox process corresponding to the formation of the quasi-reversible couple copper(II)/copper(III). The ratio of cathodic and anodic peak current values indicates that the couple is simple one electron transfer process. These complexes also show two quasi-reversible peaks in the negative region which could be assigned as copper(II)/copper(I) and copper(I)/copper(0) couple. The cyclic voltammogram of the $[\text{CuL}^3(\text{bpy})_2]\text{Cl}_2$ complex in DMSO solution at 300 K is shown in Fig. 5.

Table 5. Redox potential for copper complexes in DMSO solution containing 0.1 M TBAP

Complex	Couple	E_{pa} (mV)	E_{pc} (mV)	I_{pa} (μA)	I_{pc} (μA)	$I_{pc}(\mu\text{A})/$ $I_{pa}(\mu\text{A})$
$[\text{CuL}^1(\text{bpy})_2]\text{Cl}_2$	Cu ^{II} /Cu ^{III}	129.41	58.83	56.25	59.38	1.05
	Cu ^{II} /Cu ^I	-247.05	-905.88	53.13	87.50	1.64
	Cu ^I /Cu ⁰	-964.71	-1164.71	57.5	61.25	1.06
$[\text{CuL}^3(\text{bpy})_2]\text{Cl}_2$	Cu ^{II} /Cu ^I	81.83	-27.25	35.00	36.37	1.03
	Cu ^I /Cu ⁰	-245.45	-772.71	33.33	38.33	1.15

It shows two well defined one electron transfer redox peaks, corresponding to the formation of the copper(II)/copper(I) and copper(I)/copper(0) couple.

Fig. 5. Cyclic voltammogram of $[\text{CuL}^3(\text{bpy})_2]\text{Cl}_2$ complex in DMSO solution (0.1 M TBAP); scan rate 100 mV s^{-1} .

The powder XRD diffraction patterns are recorded for all the complexes in the range of $2\theta = 3\text{--}80^\circ$. The patterns are found to be similar with sharp peak indicating the crystalline nature of the complexes. The X-ray powder diffractograms of the copper complexes are given in Fig. 6.

Antibacterial studies : The *in vitro* antimicrobial activity of the synthesized complexes (0.1 mol) was done using well-diffusion method against Gram-positive bacteria viz. *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Bacillus subtilis* and Gram-negative bacteria *Salmonella*

Fig. 6. Powder XRD pattern of (a) $[\text{CuL}^1(\text{bpy})_2]\text{Cl}_2$, (b) $[\text{CuL}^2(\text{bpy})_2]\text{Cl}_2$ and (c) $[\text{ZnL}^1(\text{bpy})_2]\text{Cl}_2$.

typhi and *Escherichia coli* and the data of the complexes are summarized in Table 6. A comparative study of the ligands and the complexes indicates that the complexes exhibit higher activity than the free ligand and the control. Such increased activity of the complexes can be explained on the basis of the Overtone's concept and the Tweedy's chelation theory^{24,25}.

Experimental

Anhydrous grade methanol and DMSO were obtained from Fisher Scientific. Microanalytical data, ^1H NMR, ^{13}C NMR and FAB-mass spectra of the compounds were performed at the Regional Sophisticated Instrumentation Centre, Central Drug Research Institute, Lucknow (RSIC, CDRI). The FAB-mass spectrum of the complex was recorded on a Jeol SX 102/DA-6000 mass spectrometer/

Table 6. Antimicrobial activity of the synthesized compounds (zone of inhibition in mm)

Compd.	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>K. pneumoniae</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>S. typhi</i>	<i>B. subtilis</i>
Ampicillin	12	24	16	13	17
bpy	7	11	6	7	9
L ¹	8	9	13	11	5
L ²	6	6	12	8	6
L ³	9	10	7	14	12
$[\text{CuL}^1(\text{bpy})_2]\text{Cl}_2$	11	13	21	23	13
$[\text{CuL}^2(\text{bpy})_2]\text{Cl}_2$	15	14	13	14	11
$[\text{CuL}^3(\text{bpy})_2]\text{Cl}_2$	16	16	23	19	16
$[\text{ZnL}^1(\text{bpy})_2]\text{Cl}_2$	13	18	19	15	9
$[\text{ZnL}^2(\text{bpy})_2]\text{Cl}_2$	10	13	17	21	14
$[\text{ZnL}^3(\text{bpy})_2]\text{Cl}_2$	14	16	15	20	17

Data system using Argon/Xenon (6 kV, 10 mA) as the FAB gas. The accelerating voltage was 10 kV and the spectra were recorded at room temperature using *m*-nitrobenzylalcohol (NBA) as the matrix. The metals, in general estimated gravimetrically as their oxides²⁶ by fusion with ammonium oxalate. The IR spectra of the samples were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 783 spectrophotometer in 4000–200 cm⁻¹ range using KBr as solvent. The UV-Vis spectra were recorded on a Shimadzu UV-1601 spectrophotometer. The X-band ESR spectra of the complexes were recorded in DMSO at 300 K and 77 K at IIT, Mumbai using TCNE (tetracyanoethylene) as the *g*-marker. Magnetic susceptibility measurements of the complexes were carried out using Guoy balance using copper sulphate as the calibrant. Electrochemical studies were carried out using EG & G Princeton Applied Research Potentiostat/Galvanostat Model 273A, controlled by M270 software. CV measurements were performed using a glassy carbon working electrode, platinum wire auxiliary electrode and an Ag/AgCl reference electrode. Tetrabutylammoniumperchlorate (TBAP) was used as the supporting electrolyte. All solutions were purged with N₂ for 30 min prior to each set of experiments. The powder X-ray diffractograms were recorded on JEOL (Japan) JDX 8030 X-ray diffractometer using CuK_α radiations ($\lambda = 1.5418 \text{ \AA}$). The X-ray diffractograms were scanned in the 2θ ranges of 3–80°. The molar conductance of the complexes was measured in DMSO solution using a 305 Systronic conductivity bridge.

Antibacterial activity : The *in vitro* biological screening effects of the investigated compounds were tested against the bacteria *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Bacillus subtilis*, *Salmonella typhi* and *Escherichia coli* by the well-diffusion method, using agar as the nutrient medium. The test solutions were prepared by dissolving the compounds in DMSO. In a typical procedure²⁷, a well was made on the agar medium inoculated with microorganisms. The well was filled with the test solution using micropipette and the plate was incubated at 35 °C for 24 h. During this period, the test solution was diffused and the growth of the inoculated microorganisms was affected. The inhibition zone developed on the plate was measured.

Synthesis of 3,4-substituted β -diketone ligands : The ligands used were prepared by the following reported method²⁸. The ethanolic solution (20 mL) of salicylaldehyde (50 mmol, 6.1 mL) and acetylacetone (50 mmol, 5 mL)/methylacetoacetate (50 mmol, 5.8 mL)/acetoacetanilide

(50 mmol, 8.85 g) was cooled for 1 h under freezing mixture. To the cooled solution 1 mL of piperidine was added dropwise and stirred for *ca.* 1 h. The resultant mixture was kept at 0 °C for *ca.* 24 h. The product separated was filtered and recrystallized in ethanol.

Synthesis of mixed ligand complexes : The complexes were prepared by mixing the appropriate molar quantity of ligands and the metal salts using the following procedure. An ethanolic solution (10 mL) of 3,4-substituted β -diketone L¹/L²/L³ [(5 mmol, 1.02 g)/(5 mmol, 1.1 g)/(5 mmol, 1.405 g)] was stirred with the ethanolic solution (5 mL) of copper chloride (5 mmol, 0.67 g) for *ca.* 5 h. To the above mixture, an ethanolic solution (5 mL) of 2,2'-bipyridine (10 mmol, 1.56 g) was added, and the stirring was continued for *ca.* 1 h. The solid product obtained was filtered and washed with ethanol.

Acknowledgement

The author expresses his sincere thanks to the Head, Department of Chemistry, Principal and College Managing Board for providing research facilities and moral support.

References

1. K. Jeyasubramanian, S. A. Samath, S. Thambidurai, R. Murugesan and S. K. Ramalingam, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1995, **20**, 76.
2. M. Raman, S. K. Ramalingam, K. Jeyasubramanian and W. Shanthi, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1995, **34**, 919.
3. S. A. Samath, M. Raman, N. Raman, K. Jeyasubramanian and S. K. Ramalingam, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1992, **19**, 1315.
4. N. Raman, A. Kulandaisamy and A. Shunmugasundaram, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 2001, **26**, 131.
5. A. V. Ablov, *Russ. J. Inorg. Chem.*, 1961, **6**, 157.
6. D. M. Palade, A. V. Ablov and V. N. Zubarev, *Russ. J. Inorg. Chem.*, 1969, **14**, 227.
7. S. Brini, R. Bucci, V. Carunchio and G. Grassinistrizza, *J. Coord. Chem.*, 1998, **17**, 221.
8. H. Chowdhury, J. Banerjee, S. H. Rahaman, D. Bose and B. K. Ghosh, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2004, **43**, 1112.
9. P. K. Panchal and M. N. Patel, *Synth. React. Inorg. Metal-Org. Chem.*, 2004, **34**, 1277.
10. K. M. Patel, N. H. Patel, K. N. Patel and M. N. Patel, *Synth. React. Inorg. Metal-Org. Chem.*, 2000, **30**, 1953.
11. P. P. Dholakiya and M. N. Patel, *Synth. React. Inorg. Metal-Org. Chem.*, 2002, **32**, 819.

12. M. S. Luth, L. E. Kapinos, B. Song, B. Lippert and H. Sigel, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1999, 357.
13. B. Song and H. Sigel, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1998, **37**, 2066.
14. N. Raman, C. Thangaraja and S. Johnson Raja, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2005, **44**, 693.
15. N. Raman, A. Sakthivel, J. Dhaveethu Raja and K. Rajasekaran, *Russ. J. Inorg. Chem.*, 2008, **53**, 254.
16. W. J. Geary, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1971, **7**, 81.
17. G. De Munno, V. Walter, G. Viau, F. Llort, J. Faus and M. Julve, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1998, **37**, 1458.
18. K. Nakamoto, "Infrared and Raman Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", 3rd ed., Wiley Interscience, New York, 1997.
19. A. B. P. Lever, "Inorganic Electronic Spectroscopy", 2nd ed., Elsevier, New York, 1968.
20. A. L. Sharma, I. O. Singh, M. A. Singh, H. R. Singh, R. M. Kadam, M. K. Bhide and M. D. Sastry, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 2001, **26**, 532.
21. B. J. Hathaway and A. A. G. Tomlinson, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1970, **5**, 1.
22. S. Antosik, N. M. D. Brown, A. A. Mc Connel and A. L. Porte, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1969, 545.
23. J. F. Boas, R. H. Dunhil, J. R. Pilbrow, R. C. Srivastava and T. D. Smith, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1969, 94.
24. R. S. Srivastava, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1981, **56**, 55.
25. N. Dharmaraj, P. Viswanathamoorathi and K. Natarajan, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 2001, **26**, 105.
26. R. J. Angellici, "Synthesis and Techniques in Inorganic Chemistry", W. B. Saunders Company, 1969.
27. M. J. Pelczar, E. S. C. Chan and N. R. Krig, "Microbiology", 5th ed., Wiley Interscience, New York, 1998.
28. K. Uehara, M. Ito and M. Tanaka, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1973, **46**, 1566.